

A CLOUD DETECTION MODEL FOR MULTISPECTRAL SENSORS: APPLICATIONS TO WFI CAMERA ON AMAZONIA-1, CBERS-4 AND CBERS-4A SATELLITES

Aluizio Brito Maia¹; Fernanda Silva Clementino¹; Camilo Daleles Rennó¹; Yosio Edemir Shimabukuro¹; Ramon Batista dos Santos¹; Monique Calderaro da Rocha Santos¹; Karolina Chacon Armstrong²

¹ Remote Sensing Postgraduate Program (PGSER), Coordination of Teaching, Research and Extension (COEPE), National Institute for Space Research (INPE), São José dos Campos, Brazil. aluizio.maia@inpe.br; fernanda.clementino@inpe.br; camilo.renno@inpe.br; yosio.shimabukuro@inpe.br; ramon.santos@inpe.br; monique.santos@inpe.br

<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-0056-6157>

<https://orcid.org/0009-0000-2267-651X>

<https://orcid.org/0000-0001-9920-4473>

<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-1469-8433>

<https://orcid.org/0009-0009-0010-919X>

<https://orcid.org/0009-0002-2880-5049>

² Institute for Applied Economic Research (IPEA), The Directorate of Studies and Policies on the State, Institutions, and Democracy (Diest), Rio de Janeiro, Brazil.

karolina.armstrong@ipea.gov.br

<https://orcid.org/0009-0007-9099-2291>

ABSTRACT. Cloud cover in remote sensing optical images is a recurring challenge in data selection and processing. Thus, cloud masks creation is an important preprocessing step. Many methods have been developed to detect and mask clouds, however, few have been conducted using only images with RGB-NIR bands and fewer have looked to create a routine of cloud masking for Brazilian satellites that could be dynamic and operationalizable. In this study, we propose a cloud detection model in RGB-NIR images of the WFI camera onboard of Brazilian satellites in orbit. Objectively, we propose that the model should be easily and dynamically replicable. The model had a G.A of 95%, with a f1-score of 0.9502 and a specificity of 0.9572. The application for the second study area (WFI/CBERS-4A) had a G.A of 94.8%, decreasing only 0.2% from the original model, with a f1-score of 0.944 and a specificity of 0.89. Finally, when applying the model for the third area, there was a higher decrease of the global accuracy (-11.9%), being 83.1%, with a f1-score of 0.8022 and a specificity of 0.98. In general, the method is simple and produces good results, its potential can be replicated using the WFI sensor.

Keywords: Cloud Masking; Spectral indexes; Brazilian Satellites; Decision Tree; Rpart

RESUMEN. La cobertura de nubes en las imágenes de teledetección óptica es un desafío recurrente en la selección y el procesamiento de datos. Para ello, la creación de máscaras de nubes es un paso previo al procesamiento importante. Existen varios métodos utilizados para detectar y enmascarar nubes, sin embargo, pocos estudios han sido realizados utilizando imágenes sólo con las bandas RGB-NIR y aún menos estudios han buscado crear una rutina de creación de máscaras de nubes para satélites brasileños que sea dinámica y operativa. En este estudio, proponemos un modelo de detección de nubes en imágenes RGB-NIR de la cámara WFI a bordo de satélites brasileños en órbita. Objetivamente, el modelo pretendía ser replicable fácil y dinámicamente. El modelo presentó una precisión global del 95%, con un F1-score de 0,9502 y una especificidad de 0,9572. Con la aplicación al área de estudio 2 (WFI/CBERS-4A), la precisión general cayó sólo un 0,2%, alcanzando el 94,8%, con un F1-Score de 0,944 y una especificidad de 0,89. Finalmente, al aplicar el modelo al área de estudio 3, hubo una mayor caída en la precisión global del -11,9%, alcanzando el 83,1%, con un F1-Score de 0,8022 y una especificidad de 0,98. En general el método es sencillo y produce buenos resultados, se ve su potencial de ser replicable a otras áreas utilizando el sensor WFI.

Palabras-clave: Máscara de nube; Índices Espectrales; Satélites Brasileños; Árbol de Decision; Rpart.

RESUMO. A cobertura de nuvens em imagens ópticas de sensoriamento remoto é um desafio recorrente na seleção e no processamento dos dados. Para tanto, a criação de máscaras de nuvens é uma etapa de pré-processamento importante. Diversos são os métodos utilizados para detectar e mascarar nuvens, entretanto, poucos estudos foram conduzidos utilizando imagens apenas com as bandas RGB-NIR e menos estudos ainda buscaram criar uma rotina de criação de máscara de nuvens para os satélites brasileiros que fosse dinâmica e operacionalizável. Neste estudo, propomos um modelo de detecção de nuvens em imagens RGB-NIR da câmera WFI a bordo dos satélites brasileiros em órbita, objetivamente, pretendeu-se que o modelo fosse facilmente e dinamicamente replicável. O modelo apresentou uma acurácia global de 95%, tendo um F1-Score de 0.9502 e uma especificidade de 0.9572. Com a aplicação para a área de estudo 2 (WFI/CBERS-4A), a acurácia global caiu apenas 0.2%, passando a ser de 94,8%, com um F1-Score de 0.944 e uma especificidade de 0.89. Por fim, quando aplicado o modelo para a área de estudo 3, houve uma queda maior da acurácia global de -11,9%, passando a ser de 83.1%, com um F1-Score de 0.8022 e uma especificidade de 0.98. De maneira geral, o método é simples e produz bons resultados, é visto seu potencial em ser replicável para outras áreas usando o sensor WFI.

Palavras-chave: Máscara de Nuvem; Índices Espectrais; Árvore de Decisão.

1. INTRODUCTION

The presence of clouds in remote sensing images is a recurring issue, due to the obstruction of the acquisition of information about the object of interest. Clouds reduce the useful area of the image, mask features, and cast shadows, increasing the complexity of the analysis of the images. Studies on the dynamics of land use and land cover, as well as processes such as deforestation, disasters, and urban expansion, require a large amount of data in different periods of the year. There is a real need to work with classifications when utilizing this data. These classifications are sometimes affected by cloud cover, especially in areas with conditions favorable to cloud formation, such as regions with high maritime influence, extensive vegetation, or frequent high rainfall events (Candra *et al.*, 2016).

When interacting with the particles that form clouds, electromagnetic radiation is scattered in the visible wavelengths, which is the main factor of non-selective scattering. In the infrared spectrum, absorption occurs (Jensen, 2009). This reduces the amount of information registered by the sensor, making it difficult to detect targets on the surface. In that case, cloud masking is an important preprocessing step to the use of partially cloud covered images.

Cloud masks are sometimes already included in the data acquisition of certain remote sensing products, eliminating the need for a hard computationally process beforehand. However, some obstacles necessitate the development of algorithms, methods, and techniques for cloud detection. One such challenge is that users can have less control over the accuracy of cloud detection in ready-to-use products, potentially resulting in the loss of information regarding important targets. Additionally, a significant issue in the use of automatic algorithms is that many of them rely on the use of Thermal Infrared (TIR) bands. Therefore, RGB-NIR optical systems, such as those found in the CBERS family and Amazonia-1 satellites, may have limited applications.

In this context, the objective of this study was to demonstrate the potential application of the WFI camera onboard the CBERS-4, CBERS-4A, and Amazonia-1 satellites by presenting a model for cloud detection using only spectral attributes. The method involves a simple classification process using spectral indexes and utilizing a decision tree algorithm to create the cloud mask. The model was tested on different surfaces. The objective of the method is to

be practical and easily replicable, with the aim of using it in dynamic applications such as rapid responses to disasters and deforestation processes.

2. METHODOLOGY

The work was performed in different processing stages as shown in Figure 1, the general steps of the study are detailed below. The calculation of spectral indexes, step (1), was conducted using the Qgis software (QGIS Development Team, 2024), using the raster calculator function, followed by the thresholding process, step (2) also conducted using the Qgis software. The selection of attributes, step (3), was conducted using the attribute selection through a cross-validation process, finally, the decision tree used rpart algorithm, implemented in R language, in the software Rstudio (Rstudio Team, 2024).

Figure 1. General Flowchart.
Source: Elaborated by the authors (2024)

2.1. Study Area

Three scenes under different Land Use and Land Cover conditions were selected for analysis using imagery captured by the WFI sensor on the Amazonia-1, CBERS-4, and CBERS-4A satellites. The WFI/CBERS-4 image focused on a scene between the states of Maranhão, Pará, and Piauí in northern and northeastern Brazil. This region is characterized by dense vegetation, where evapotranspiration significantly influences cloud formation and hydrological cycles. Additionally, the area experiences oceanic influence, further contributing to cloud cover.

The WFI/Amazonia-1 image targeted a portion of the Amazonian biome, encompassing the states of Amazonas, Pará, Mato Grosso, and Rondônia. This region is dominated by vegetation and boasts large water bodies that release significant amounts of water vapor into the atmosphere. Finally, the CBERS-4A image centered on an area between the states of Minas Gerais and São Paulo in southeastern Brazil. This region exhibits high landscape fragmentation, with land use primarily dedicated to crop production and forestry. Additionally, the area includes large urban centers. This approach capitalizes on the fact that different land cover patterns interact distinctly with electromagnetic radiation, as does the atmosphere over these areas.

Figure 2. Location map of the study areas, in (A) Amazonia-1 scene, (B) CBERS-4 scene and (C) CBERS-4A scene. all in color composition (RGB).

Source: Elaborated by the authors (2024).

2.2. WFI sensor

The images utilized are originally from the Wide Field Imager (WFI), onboard the satellites CBERS-4, CBERS-4A, and Amazonia-1. It used images with the processing level L4, which had radiometric and geometric correction; these images were converted to values of Top of Atmosphere (TOA) reflectance.

Table 1. Sensor specifications and bands used.

Wide Field Imager (WFI)	CBERS-4	CBERS-4A	AMAZONIA-1
Date	02/28/2022	12/11/2023	12/28/2023
Spatial Resolution	64 m	55 m	65 m
Swath	866 km	684 km	850 km
Revisit Time	5 days		
Blue Band	0.45 - 0.52 μm		
Green Band	0.52 - 0.59 μm		
Red Band	0.63 - 0.69 μm		
Near Infrared Band	0.77 - 0.89 μm		

Sources: INPE, 2005; Epiphanyo, 2009; INPE, 2021.

2.3 Parameters for the Construction of The Cloud Mask

For the parametrization, it was selected and used spectral indexes that had shown good results.

2.3.1 Whiteness Index (WI)

Whiteness Index (WI) is an index proposed by Gómez-Chova *et al.* (2007) that analyzes the presence of whiteness in pixels to identify clouds. This method performs well for dense clouds, but it can underestimate non-cumulus clouds. The WI calculation is given by:

$$WI = \sum_{i=1}^3 \left| \frac{Band_i - M}{M} \right| \quad (1)$$

which $Band_i$ is referred to bands R($i=1$), G($i=2$) and B($i=3$), and $M = 0.25B + 0.375G + 0.375R$.

2.3.2 Haze Optimized Transformation (HOT)

The HOT Index (Haze Optimized Transformation), proposed by Zhang *et al.* (2002), analyzes the spatial distribution of clouds, originally in Landsat images. The index has several adaptations, like its use with time-series and further applications in aquatic systems (Zhu and Helmer, 2018). It is widely used due to its good results in detecting translucent clouds, such as cirrus, and haze. Although originally proposed for Landsat images, it has shown good results with MUX/CBERS-4 and AWF/CBERS-4 images (Marujo *et al.*, 2017; Silva and Liporace, 2016). The index can be calculated by the following formula:

$$HOT = B - 0.45 \cdot R - 0.08 \quad (2)$$

where B is the blue band and R is the red band.

2.3.3 Cloud Index (CI)

Zhai *et al.* (2018) proposed an algorithm based on spectral indexes that integrates cloud and cloud shadow detection by creating two indexes: CI (Cloud Index) and CSI (Cloud Shadow Index). The method prioritizes practicality and low computational cost. Primarily, the index is designed for sensors equipped with the Short Wave Infrared Channel (SWIR). Although the primary use of the index is with sensors that have the SWIR band, the authors proposed an alternative way for sensors lacking it. This alternative method describes the bright property of clouds through:

$$CI = \frac{3 \cdot NIR}{B + G + R} \quad (3)$$

where NIR is the near infrared, B is blue, G is green and R is red bands.

2.3.4 Near Infrared Shadow and Cloud Detection Index - NIR-SCD

We propose a new index, based on the idea of HOT adapted to water surfaces (Zhu and Helmer, 2018), called Near Infrared Shadow and Cloud Detection Index (NIR-SCD), which utilizes the near-infrared (NIR) band to enhance detection of cirrus clouds while simultaneously identifying cloud shadows. The NIR-SCD is designed to minimize confusion between cirrus clouds and water surfaces, particularly during flood events and near large bodies of water. This is achieved by mitigating the influence of high NIR reflectance from water on the spectral response of the index. The index is calculated by:

$$NIRSCD = B - 0.45 \cdot R - 0.16 \cdot NIR \quad (4)$$

where B is the blue band, R is the red band and NIR is the near infrared band.

2.3.5 Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI)

One of the indexes used, NDVI, is applied to verify the presence and condition of health of vegetation, with its values varying between -1 to 1. In the present study, NDVI was used mainly to help in the detection of pure cloud free pixels. Its calculation is given by the equation:

$$NDVI = \frac{NIR - R}{NIR + R} \quad (5)$$

where NIR is in the near infrared band and R is the red band.

2.4 Thresholding Process

The thresholding was employed to evaluate the spectral indexes in distinguishing cloud free pixels from cloud pixels. This process resulted in a binary image, where pixels with a value of "0" represent surface targets, and pixels with a value of "1" represent clouds.

The processing was made through the Qgis software, using the LF Tools plug-in, with the binary thresholding function. The above-mentioned indexes were used as the input raster, as well as sample polygons (100 cloud and 100 non-cloud samples). The threshold established was the quantile (2% - 98%). This process was carried out for the three scenes and for each of the spectral indexes, with NDVI being the only index that used the non-cloud samples for processing.

2.5 Decision Tree

2.5.1 - Rpart Algorithm

Starting from the thresholding process, attributes that could potentially contribute to the construction of the mask were selected and used as input parameters for the classifier. This selection prioritized attributes with higher global accuracy. For the classification process, the Recursive Partitioning and Regression Trees - rpart algorithm (Therneau, 2023a) was used.

In this algorithm, the decision tree is constructed in two main steps. First, the variable that best distinguishes the data into two groups (in our case, clouds and non-clouds) is identified. Rpart utilizes impurity metrics (i.e., Gini Impurity Index and Twoing) to select these variables. Next, the data are split again, and this process is applied to each group recursively

until all groups reach a minimum size or no further improvement in data division is possible (Therneau, 2023b).

Knowing this process, many hyperparameters can be adjusted to optimize the classification model for the dataset. In this context, univariate tests were conducted, individually changing each of the parameters and analyzing which combinations produced the best results, in terms of Global Accuracy and F1-Score. Once the best combination was identified, the hyperparameters were defined: 10 for MinSplit, 10/3 for MinBucket, 0.001 for cp, 5 for MaxSurrogate, 1 for Maxcompete and 20 for Maxdepth

Table 2: Hyperparameters Selected for The Final Decision Tree

Hyperparameter	MinSplit	MinBucket	cp	MaxSurrogate	Maxcompete	Maxdepth
Value	10	10/3	0.001	5	1	20

Source: Elaborated by the authors (2024).

2.5.2 - Sampling and Classification Process

The sampling was conducted using an iterative simple random sampling method, gathering samples in areas that are spectrally and spatially representative. Altogether, 610 samples were collected for the image of Amazonia-1 (307 of clouds and 303 of surface), 400 samples for the image of CBERS-4 (200 of clouds and 200 of surface), and 400 samples for the image of CBERS-4A (200 of clouds and 200 of surface).

To analyze the predictive capacity of the model when applied to new data, the classifier was trained only on the Amazonia-1 data. The trained model was then applied to the data from the other study areas. From the Amazonia-1 study area samples, 70% were used for training and 30% for testing. In contrast, for the other study areas, 100% of the samples were used for testing.

Due to the intrinsic randomness of the sample separation, the k-fold technique was applied. In this technique, the data is divided into k subsets (it was chosen 10 subsets) and trained k times. In each iteration, one of the folds is retained as the validation set, while the others are used as the training set. The model's performance is evaluated k times, and then the evaluations are averaged. This technique is used to analyze whether the model is underfitting or overfitting. For a comprehensive analysis of the results, the confusion matrix of the classifications was used. From this matrix, the following metrics were calculated to assess the model's performance: Global Accuracy, Sensibility, Precision, F1-Score and Specificity.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The use of spectral attributes selected by the thresholding process generated the decision tree shown in Figure 3. It can be seen that with the predefined complexity of the tree, it showed good results in distinguishing a considerable part of the samples using only nodes 9 and 2. Using a more complex tree than necessary can lead to overfitting. However, given the heterogeneity of clouds, capturing minimal details in spectral patterns is important, and nodes 4, 6, and 10 can detect those details. Regarding the overfitting problem, cross-validation using the K-fold technique made good use of the data, and using the mean of the results decreased the risk of overfitting.

Related to the spectral indices, the potential of the HOT index in detecting clouds that have already been established, was seen. However, it has limitations in more opaque clouds. The WI and NIR-SCD indexes can cover those targets, so the combination of these indexes can detect the vast majority of cloud types. The decision tree likely discarded the Cloud Index due to its correlation with some of the other indices.

Figure 3. Final Decision Tree for the Model
Source: Elaborated by the authors (2024).

The results demonstrated satisfactory statistical metrics. For the trained model using the Amazonia-1 image, an overall accuracy of 95% was achieved, with a precision of 0.9577 and sensitivity of 0.9444. These values indicate that the model is inclusive but could be improved in its accuracy in detecting actual clouds. The balance between these metrics is favorable, as evidenced by an F1-score of 0.9502. Additionally, a specificity of 0.9572 indicates that the model detects true negatives well.

When applying the model to the test areas using the CBERS-4A and CBERS-4 images, the results remained satisfactory. For the CBERS-4A image, the overall accuracy decreased by only 0.2%, to 94.8%. However, the other metrics experienced slightly greater declines: precision decreased to 0.92, sensitivity to 0.9254, and F1-Score to 0.944. The most significant decrease was in specificity, which dropped to 0.89. This decrease in specificity may be attributed to the presence of different non-cloud targets in the area.

Finally, there was a higher decrease of the metrics for the CBERS-4 image, a decrease of 11.9%, with an accuracy of 83.1%, however, the precision increased with a value of 0.9722, but the sensitivity had lower results, 0.6829, so the F1-Score was of 0.8022. The specificity on the other hand, had the better results among the areas, with a value of 0.98, which shows that the model could catch the differences in not-cloud targets. It's assumed that the lower statistical metrics results are associated with the fact that the area is even more heterogeneous, and the clouds are smaller. Many of the false-positives samples are in the areas of the beach and in the *Lençois Maranhenses*, which have a bright surface. The final cloud masks can be seen in Figure 4.

Figure 4. Comparison between original images and cloud mask.
Source: Elaborated by the authors (2024).

3. CONCLUSIONS

The use of spectral indexes to identify clouds proved effective. When analyzing the statistical results obtained, we can see that the model obtained is replicable for other areas, since the study areas encompass different land covers and, therefore, the atmospheric conditions also differ. Also, with different cloud types, opaque clouds and more translucent clouds were identified and classified by the model. For translucent clouds, which are usually misidentified and misclassified, using the NIR-SCD and WI indexes we obtained satisfactory results, showing the model's applicability in identifying different cloud types. There were challenges related to the detection of False-Positives, mostly on bright surfaces like beach and sand..

For future works, it is recommended the inclusion of cloud shadow detection methods in the model, although NIR-SCD effectively can detect shadows as well, the accuracy control in shadow detections wasn't directly observed, once the work's objective was mainly to think of a rapid methodology to detect clouds. Finally, it's suggested to use ensemble machine learning models, such as random forest, knowing mainly the potential of seeing uncertainty in the images.

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